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Websites as a tool for advertising and promotional work of publishing houses

Olena POHRIBNAPhD in Philology, Associate
ProfessorBohdan Khmelnytskyi National
University of Cherkasy81, Shevchenka Boulevard, 18031,
Cherkasy, Ukraine

pogribna_olena@ukr.net

ORCID 0000-0002-1564-5448

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The article analyses websites as a tool for advertising and promotional work of publishing houses. The web resources of leading Ukrainian publishing houses (“Old Lion Publishing House”, “A-ba-ba-ha-la-ma-ha”, “Nash Format”, “Family Leisure Club”, “Ranok”, “Osnovy”, “Folio”, “Vivat”, “Vihola”, “Knigolove”, “ArtBooks”, “Abuk”) were studied.

The article focuses on the advantages of creating and filling websites as a PR technology in the publishing industry, on their capabilities for promotional activities of a publishing house to fully represent the company on the Internet; to place a large amount of various information about the publishing house activities; to clearly structure all content into sections according to the necessary criteria; to facilitate the audience’s access to the publishing house products (sale of books and other goods via the Internet); to sell not only those books that are currently available in the publishing house, but also pre-sell them, announce new products, leave a request for books that are temporarily out of stock; post complete information about the publishing house, a clearly structured catalogue of books and other products, a photo gallery, video reviews and book trailers, as well as a news section and various forms of interaction with readers (blogs, forums, feedback pages, etc.) maintain interactive communication with the audience; hold photo contests, interactive games, quests, creative contests, etc. for the audience through the website; post extensive annotations to books, book previews, video reviews, book trailers; perform a quick search for the necessary information; duplicate the most important information in several sections of the website; issue subscriptions through the website; cooperate with other publishers and online bookstores; provide gift certificates.

The types of the leading Ukrainian publishing houses content are also studied and classified, with considerable attention paid to the rubrication of websites and the multi-level and extensive structure of books and other products catalogues.

Moreover, the article analyses the type of web resource most often chosen by publishers. It was found that preference is given to online stores and corporate websites.

The article also presents the rules for creating, structuring and filling websites that publishers follow, focusing on the needs and interests of their target audience and the types of content.

Keywords: publishing house website, book products promotion, advertising and PR activities of publishing houses, website content structuring, website sectioning, book products catalogue, website usability.

ВЕБСАЙТИ ЯК ІНСТРУМЕНТ РЕКЛАМНО-ПРОМОЦІЙНОЇ РОБОТИ ВИДАВНИЦТВ

Олена ПОГРІБНА

канд. філол. н., доц.

Черкаський національний університет імені Богдана Хмельницького,
бульвар Шевченка, 81, 18031, Черкаси, Україна

pogribna_olena@ukr.net

ORCID 0000-0002-1564-5448

У статті проаналізовано вебсайти як засіб рекламно-промоційної роботи видавництва. Досліджено вебресурси провідних українських видавництв («Видавництво Старого Лева», «А-ба-ба-га-ла-ма-га», «Наш Формат», «Клуб сімейного дозвілля», «Ранок», «Основи», «Фоліо», «Віват», «Віхола», «Книголав», «ArtBooks», «Абук»).

Акцентовано увагу на перевагах створення й наповнення сайтів як PR-технології в видавничій галузі, на їхніх можливостях для промоційної діяльності видавництва — повноцінно представляти підприємство в інтернеті; розміщувати велику кількість різноманітної інформації про діяльність видавництва; чітко структурувати весь контент у рубрики за потрібними критеріями; полегшувати доступ аудиторії до продукції видавництва (продаж книг та інших товарів через інтернет); продавати не тільки ті книги, які зараз наявні у видавництві, а й здійснювати попередній продаж, анонсувати новинки, залишати заявку на ті книги, яких тимчасово немає в продажу; розміщувати повну інформацію про видавництво, чітко структурований каталог книжок та іншої продукції, фотогалерею, відеоогляди й буктрейлери, а також новинний блок та різноманітні форми взаємодії з читачами (блоги, форуми, сторінки з відгуками тощо); підтримувати інтерактивний зв'язок з аудиторією; проводити через сайт для аудиторії фотоконкурси, інтерактивні ігри, квести, творчі конкурси тощо; розміщувати розлогі анотації до книг, прев'ю книжок, відеогорталки, буктрейлери; здійснювати швидкий пошук необхідної інформації; дублювати найважливішу інформацію в декількох рубриках сайту; оформлювати підписки через сайт; співпрацювати з іншими видавництвами та інтернет-книгарнями; оформлювати подарункові сертифікати.

Також досліджено й класифіковано типи контенту провідних українських видавництв; водночас значну увагу приділено рубрикації сайтів і багаторівневій та розгалуженій структурі каталогів книг та інших товарів.

Крім того, проаналізовано, який вид вебресурсу найчастіше обирають видавництва. З'ясовано, що перевага надається інтернет-магазинам і корпоративним сайтам.

Також стаття репрезентує правила створення, структурування й наповнення вебсайтів, яких дотримуються видавництва, орієнтуючись на потреби й інтереси своєї цільової аудиторії та на типи розміщеного контенту.

Ключові слова: сайт видавництва, промоція книжкової продукції, рекламна й PR-діяльність видавництв, структурування контенту вебсайту, рубрикація сайту, каталог книжкової продукції, юзабіліті сайту.

The relevance of the problem

Even though the modern audience prefers social networks to receive various types of information, the websites of organisations (and publishing houses are no exception) do not lose their relevance. Professor M. Tymoshyk (2010), emphasising the advantages of Internet resources for both the reader and the publisher, notes: “The importance of such sites lies in the fact that they contain not only general information about the publisher and a list of books available for sale, but also reviews of the best editions, fragments of electronic versions of individual chapters, information about the next new releases” (p. 390). That is why today all publishing houses, except for some regional ones, must have their own websites (compared to the 10s of the 21st century, when this business was just emerging in Ukraine and only a small number of publishing houses had their own websites: “Geneza”, “Osnovy”, “Smoloskyp”, “Yurinkom”, “Tekhnika”).

In addition, many modern people prefer online shopping, and publishers sell their products online primarily through their websites, while other communication channels, including social media, publish a lot of information about the publisher as part of their advertising and PR activities, but redirect readers to the website to order or pre-order a book.

State study of the problem

The issue of advertising and promotional work of publishing houses has been actively studied since the beginning of the twenty-first century (M. Tymoshyk (2005, 2010); V. Tkachenko et al. (2008); H. Kliuchkovska (2000); V. Shpak (2015); T. Yezhyzhanska (2016, 2017a, 2017b, 2017c, 2018a, 2018b, 2018c); N. Zelinska (2014); I. Kopystynska and T. Hrynivskyi (2015); I. Kopystynska (2018), Yu. Melnyk and O. Drachuk (2010), O. Skiban (2014, 2016, 2017, 2019); O. Skochynets (2010, 2011); I. Slavinska (2012); A. Sudyn (2008); L. Tanchyn (2008)).

Scholars focus on the web resources of publishing houses, but either only name the sites among other modern book promotion technologies (O. Kanshyna (2017); O. Maniatina (2023); I. Vikyrchak (2018)) or briefly describe them (K. Havryliuk and M. Rudkivska (2020); Z. Hryhorova (2020); O. Skiban (2014, 2016)).

A separate study of publishing houses' websites as a factor of book promotion is the article by N. Ivanova (2016), in which the author analysed the multifunctionality, architectonic organisation and web resources content of two Ukrainian publishing houses: “Folio” and “Old Lion Publishing House”.

The study analyses theoretical sources with recommendations on creating and maintaining websites (V. Korolko and O. Nekrasova (2009); V. Kuruch and A. Yakovets (2012); Ye. Ponomarenko (2011), as well as advice from specialists of the Internet marketing agency “Webpromo” on usability and increasing website conversion).

The source base of the study is the websites of leading Ukrainian publishing houses that have been ranked first in various ratings in recent years, which are focused on the market, on the needs of different members of their target audience, and constantly use modern promotional technologies, i.e., those publishing houses whose brand is recognisable: “Old Lion Publishing House” (<https://starylev.com.ua>), “A-ba-ba-ha-la-ma-ha” (<https://store.ababahalamaha.com.ua>), “Nash Format” (<https://nashformat.ua>), “Family Leisure Club” (<https://ksd.ua>; <https://bookclub.ua/>), “Ranok” (<https://www.ranok.com.ua>), “Osnovy” (<https://osnovypublishing.com>), “Folio” (<https://folio.com.ua>), “Vivat” (<https://vivat.com.ua>), “Vikhola” (<https://www.vikhola.com>), “Knigolove” (<https://knigolove.ua>), “ArtBooks” (<https://artbooks.ua>), “Abuk” (<https://abuk.com.ua>).

Unresolved issues

As can be seen from the sources review, there is currently no comprehensive study of the functioning and filling of leading Ukrainian publishing houses websites. In addition, Ukrainian publishers are constantly updating their web resources, using new PR tools and various communication channels to disseminate information to their audience, and improving the usability of their websites, which makes this topic relevant.

The objective of the article is a comprehensive analysis of Ukrainian publishing houses’ websites in the context of the promotion of their products and also the creation of the publishing house and its authors’ positive image, namely:

- 1) to outline the possibilities and advantages of a website as a tool for information and promotion work of an organisation;
- 2) to study and classify the types of content and the rubric of leading Ukrainian publishing houses’ websites;
- 3) to analyse what type of website is most often chosen by organisations;
- 4) to define the basic rules for creating and filling publishers’ websites.

Main material presentation

A website can be considered to be an important tool for information and promotion work of a publishing house due to its **capabilities and advantages**:

1. The official website fully represents the publishing house on the Internet. Professor M. Tymoshyk (2010) names the significant advantages of websites for a publisher: “saving money on marketing programmes, the possibility of selling goods at lower prices, providing information about the availability of books in unlimited territories, and popularising the programme of the publishing house” (p. 390).
2. The ability to post a large amount of various information about the organisation’s activities.

3. The website (unlike social media) allows you to clearly structure all content into sections according to the necessary criteria, which is especially important for various publishing products.

4. Facilitates access to the publisher's products for the audience. First and foremost, we are talking about selling books and other goods online. Some publishing houses, such as "Nash Format" and "Vivat", have an online bookstore as their official website, while "Family Leisure Club" has a separate official website and an online store. This allows readers to choose the product they need at any time and order it directly from the publisher at a lower price than in a bookstore.

5. The possibility to sell not only the books that are currently available at the publishing house. We are talking primarily about the following categories:

- Pre-sales, i.e. the sale of books that the publishing house is currently working on and will soon be published.

- Book announcements that will be available to order soon. For example, the "Family Leisure Club" offers a separate section with announcements of new titles that will soon go on sale. It provides a full description of the book and offers to leave an email address with a request. When the product is ordered later, it will be discounted, which the buyer sees immediately on the website.

- Books that are temporarily out of stock. For example, the "Family Leisure Club" website has a separate section for books and products that are popular with readers, so they were quickly sold out, but will soon be available again. The publishing house invites site visitors to leave their email addresses in a special field to receive a notification when the product is available for order.

6. A corporate website (this is the type of website that publishers choose most often) allows you to post complete information about the organisation, a clearly structured catalogue with books and other products, a photo gallery, video reviews and book trailers, as well as a news section and various forms of interaction with readers (blogs, forums, feedback pages, etc.).

7. Interactive communication with the audience: the ability to leave a review of a book or inform the publisher about a mistake that the reader has noticed in the book. For example, the "Nash Format" publishing house has created a separate subsection on its website called "Mistake in a book of Nash Format" with a Google form for reporting.

8. Holding photo contests, interactive games, quests, creative contests, etc. for the audience through the website.

9. Posting extensive abstracts to books, book previews, video wrappers, and book trailers on the website.

10. Quick search for the necessary information (primarily books) on the site using keywords, the title of the book or its author.

11. Possibility to duplicate the most important information in several sections of the site or to place the necessary section in several places on the site, for example, in the main menu, in sidebars and the footer.

12. Subscription through the website (usually via email) to be informed about new books, special offers, news, events from the publisher, etc.

13. Cooperation between publishing houses, when one publishing house offers products of other Ukrainian publishing houses on its website as a separate item in the catalogue (“Old Lion Publishing House”, “Nash Format”, “Family Leisure Club”).

14. Publishers, like the vast majority of other organisations, offer their clients gift certificates. You can place an order for one, as well as purchase with such a certificate, through the website.

The conducted research gives grounds to distinguish the following **types of content and sectioning** of leading Ukrainian publishing houses websites:

Organisations' websites have several *sections* that structure all the information aimed at meeting the interests of different target audiences. For example, here are the headings of several of the analysed publishing houses (the names of the headings clearly show the content of these websites):

– The “Family Leisure Club” has several websites. The main business card site contains all the information about the “Family Leisure Club” company, which combines a publishing house, a website, a network of bookstores and wholesale trade. From this site, there are hyperactive links to the page with information about the publishing house (“Mission and Goals”, “Key Areas and Series”, “World Literature Stars”, “Popular Ukrainian Authors”, “Books.KSD.ua” (online book presentations), “Book exhibitions”, “Book sales”, “Publishing house positions”, “Information for authors” (procedure for accepting and reviewing manuscripts, general requirements for works of fiction and applied literature), “Wholesale”) and other online projects of the company, including the “KSD” website itself. The latter has its own, separately developed sections: “Fiction”, “Applied”, “Children’s”, “Special Offers”, “eBooks”, “KSD Announcements”, “KSD News” (tells about the publishing house’s achievements and important innovations, event announcements, presentations of book novelties, author tours schedules, photo reports from book exhibitions, interviews with the winners of prize draws), “Book Digest” (an electronic mini-catalogue published once a month with the best books of the month by “KSD” publishing house and bestsellers of partners, shows real prices, special offers and other relevant information).

– “Nash Format”: “Books”, “All authors”, “E-books”, “TOP books”, “Contacts”, “Must Read Books”, “Video book reviews”, “Popular categories” (e-books, best books of our time, new books, business literature, historical literature, fiction, children’s books), “Consumer’s corner” (about the com-

pany, payment, delivery, loyalty programme, registration, positions, product returns, wartime FAQ, books for the Armed Forces of Ukraine); “Cooperation” (corporate cooperation, offer us a book, how to become a control reader of “Nash Format” books, creation of a high-quality Ukrainian audio-book, a mistake in a “Nash Format” book);

– “Old Lion Publishing House”: “Catalogue”, “About Us”, “Blog”, “News”, “Events”, “For Business”, “English”, “Contacts”;

– “A-ba-ba-ha-la-ma-ha”: “Our books”, “New editions”, “Bestsellers”, “In print”, “Sets”, “Harry Potter”;

– “Ranok”: “Catalogue”, “E-books”, “Promotions”, “Final Sale”, “Help”, “Catalogues”, “Publishers”, “Download a textbook”, “Submit a manuscript”, “Blog”, “Foreign rights”, “Gift cards”, “New releases”, “Coming soon”, “Stylish T-shirts for book lovers”, “Most popular categories”, “Popular series”, “Blog”, “Some facts about publishing today”, “About us”, “Media about us”, “User Agreement”;

– “Vivat”: “All Categories”, “Promotions”, “Blog”, “Authors”, “Publishers”, “For Customers”, “Company” (about the “Vivat” online store and contacts);

– “Knigolove”: “Catalogue”, “Useful information” (“Worth reading”, “Our shops”, “Orders payment and delivery”, etc.).

As mentioned above, the main function of websites is to sell publishing house products, so the section containing books and other products *catalogue*, has a multi-level branching structure.

To make it easier to find books, websites offer various filters. It should be noted that publishers are not limited to the classic search criteria (by author, by genre, by age), but offer a wide range of choices. For example, the websites of leading Ukrainian publishing houses offer the opportunity to select products by the following criteria:

– “Nash Format”: e-books (subcategories by genre), fiction (subcategories by genre), new releases (from “Nash Format” publishing house, non-fiction, fiction and children’s books), forthcoming (offer for pre-order), history, military affairs (research, military affairs, special services, world history, archeology, weapons and military equipment, history of Ukraine), business (top 30 books about business, best business books according to the Financial Times, as well as several thematic subcategories), foreign language learning (subcategories by language), documentary literature (documents, publicistics, biographies, memoirs, diary), garage sale (books with a minor defect that does not affect the readability and reading quality), art, culture (subcategories by different types of art), gifts for book lovers (gift certificates and book accessories), for parents and teachers (education, child psychology, child health, pregnancy and childbirth, pedagogy and methodology), marketing, advertising and PR, fiction in foreign languages (subcategories by genre), cooking,

drinks, gift editions and albums, leisure, hobbies, sports (games, entertainment, holidays, image, beauty, etc, collecting, anti-stress colouring books, etc.), reference books (encyclopedias, phrasebooks, dictionaries, handbooks), gifts (gift wrapping, diaries, notebooks, stickers, tableware, souvenirs, bags, art kits), atlases, maps, guidebooks, school curriculum (Ukrainian and foreign literature), periodicals, top 20 of “Nash Format”, sale up to -40%, children’s literature (subcategories by genre), audio-books (subcategories by genre), top books by Ukrainian publishers, motivational literature (popular psychology), non-fiction in foreign languages, support of new projects (collection for various projects, for example, “The Army Reads”, etc.), humanities (subcategories by type of science), gift sets, modern technologies and innovations, release announcements (in this subsection, you can read about “Nash Format’s” publishing plans and sign up for the beginning of the pre-sale), comics and graphic novels, natural and exact sciences (subcategories by types of sciences), medicine (subcategories by sections of medicine), religion, esotericism, occult sciences, Explore Ukraine/world about Ukraine (history, biographies, the Russian-Ukrainian war since 2014, Ukrainian cuisine, etc, children’s books about Ukraine, Ukrainian cuisine, etc.), symbolism, legal literature (subcategories by different types of law), educational literature, KyivBookFest (new releases presented at the KyivBookFest festival), 20 best business books according to the Financial Times; each of the subcategories has its own filters (authors, publication year, binding, language, series, price, age, translators, etc.);

– “Old Lion Publishing House”: type of product (paper books, e-books, souvenirs, sets, charity), popular filters (all products, pickup only, forthcoming, new, promotion, top sales, pre-sale), by age, sections (educational books, for teenagers, children’s, illustrated stories and fairy tales, picture books, poems for children, cardboard books, picture books, short fiction and essays, fiction, poetry, art and culture, cooking, biographies and memoirs, business and self-development, albums and art books, graphic novels, textbooks, reportage, historical topics, modern classics, comics and manga), authors, translators, designers, illustrators, tags;

– “A-ba-ba-ha-la-ma-ha”: series, genre, age group, cover type, author, translation author, illustration author, cover illustrator;

– “Family Leisure Club”: fiction (contemporary authors, romantic fiction, historical and adventure fiction, detectives, thrillers and horror, science fiction, fantasy, classical literature, comics and manga), applied (history, facts and biography, psychology, self-development and motivation, business literature, leisure and hobbies, science pop, esotericism, tarot), children’s (up to 4 years old, 4–6 years old, 7–12 years old, from 12 years old, school and educational books, developmental books, fairy tales and novels), special offers (exclusively in KSD, books of the month, KSD novelties, KSD

announcements, partner novelties, best sellers, gift books, discounted sets, bookmarks for books, sale, last copies), e-books (with the same filters as for paper books), KSD announcements;

– “Ranok”: new products, early development, school preparation (for kindergarten tutors, English for kids, early development, school preparation, creative development, interior design, literacy, inclusive education), educational literature (school management, primary school, secondary and high school, lesson preparation, reference books, dictionaries, etc.), children’s literature (books for the youngest, reading to children, wimmelbooks, children’s Bible, sticker books, encyclopedias, books for independent reading), for teenagers and youth (detectives, science fiction and fantasy, psychology, growing up, self-development, scientific and educational literature, adventure, classics, romantic fiction, contemporary fiction), comics, adult literature (fiction, non-fiction, for parents about children), games and creativity, stationery;

– “Vivat”: books (fiction, Ukrainian literature, children’s books, teenage literature, comics, manga, non-fiction, foreign language books), e-books (fiction, Ukrainian literature, non-fiction), related products (book merchandise, notebooks, stickers, bookmarks);

– “Knigolove”: books, e-books, children’s shelf, golden shelf, gifts, thriller shelf, sets, certificates; each of these categories has its own subcategories and filters.

The study analysed theoretical sources with recommendations on how to create and maintain websites (Korolko & Nekrasova, 2009, pp. 823–829; “Yuzabiliti i pidvyshchennia konversii сайту”, n.d.; Kuruch & Yakovets, 2012, pp. 131–134; Ponomarenko, 2011, et al.) and it was found that publishers generally follow these tips and have developed basic **rules** for creating, structuring, filling, and following the principles of website usability, focusing on the interests and needs of their target audience and the types of content they publish:

1. When choosing the type of website, one should be guided by the needs of the organisation and the amount of information required for publication on the Internet. The vast majority of publishing houses have chosen the following types of websites that fully meet the specifics of websites for publishing organisations:

– by functional purpose: an online store (selling books and other goods) or a corporate website (has a commercial and informational purpose, helps to form a positive image of the organisation, i.e. both selling books and informing about the activities of the publishing house);

– by type: commercial;

– in terms of updating sections frequency: dynamic.

2. The design of the analysed publishing houses websites corresponds to the corporate style.

3. The website header should contain the full name of the publishing house and the logo. The vast majority of publishers adhere to this rule, but the “Family Leisure Club” has only an abbreviation in the header, and its decoding is available in the section “About the KSD “FLC””, but not on the main page.

4. Navigation on publishers’ websites is quite convenient and understandable. Almost all of the analysed sites (except for “Nash Format”) have a clickable logo that returns the visitor from any page of the site to the main page.

5. Publishers’ websites are functional and informative, without information and graphic noise.

6. The interfaces of the analysed websites and the search for information on them are as simple as possible, access to certain materials is easy and intuitive (i.e., users of different target audiences can find the information they need quickly and easily).

7. The website footers are properly designed and contain the main and additional elements that should be placed in the bottom of the website:

- contacts;
- copyright;
- hyperlinks to social networks;
- sitemap (links to sections that repeat the structure of the site, as a rule, it is a transition to sections of book catalogues);
- legal information (privacy policy, consent to the processing of personal data, which is a very important legal norm, because readers order and pay for books from their personal accounts, i.e. leave their contacts, payment details, etc. on the website);
- public offer agreement;
- registration form, email subscription;
- address of the physical location of the publishing house and bookstores;
- re-positioning of the logo;
- information on terms of cooperation, vacancies in the publishing house;
- requirements for author’s originals;
- terms of ordering, payment and delivery of books and other goods;
- guarantees for buyers (the procedure for returning and exchanging books);
- FAQ (Frequently Asked Questions), for example: on the website of “Nash Format” publishing house “Frequently Asked Questions of Wartime”;
- benefits for regular customers;
- information about partners (often on the websites of online bookstores);
- copyright, etc.

However, the study found some deviations from the above rules. For example, “Nash Format” publishing house does not duplicate the logo in the footer, and if we take into account that the header disappears when you scroll down the web page, there is no identification with the publishing house in the basement of the site.

8. Publishing houses’ websites contain information for all target audiences: regular readers, potential buyers of goods, partners, and those looking for a job in a publishing house (vacancies).

9. The conducted research has shown that, in accordance with their focus on different target audiences, organisations have chosen the optimal website structure (two-level or multi-level main menu, headings, additional links, functional and design elements). Among the types of structures of publishers’ web resources, the predominant one is tree-like (from the main page the user goes to one of the pages of the second level, from there to one of the pages of the third level, etc.), but there are also linear (from the main page the user goes to the second page, from the second page to the third, etc.) and arbitrary (the user can go from one page to another in different ways).

10. The website must have a hyperactive link to all social networks where the pages of this publisher are present and other online resources, if any, which contributes to the successful promotion of the website on Internet platforms.

11. Competent design of all materials published on the publisher’s website.

Conclusions

1. Undoubtedly, the main task of a website is to sell books. But besides the commercial one, websites perform many other functions, primarily image and informational.

2. The site’s sectioning depends on the specifics of the publishing house and its genre and thematic focus. If the organisation chooses an online store, the menu contains categories of the book catalogue; if it is a corporate website, the catalogue is one of the sections, and besides it, the most popular sections among the analysed websites are the following: product catalogue, information about the publishing house, information about popular Ukrainian and foreign authors of this publishing house, online book presentations, book previews, contacts, information about where, besides this website, you can buy the publishing house’s products, news, blogs, offers from the publishing house, selections of the best books and bestsellers, promotions, offers of cooperation, information for authors on the procedure for accepting and reviewing manuscripts and general requirements for works of literature of various genres.

3. Publishers use their websites as online stores and offer catalogues in which products are classified into different sections and subsections. In addition, publishers use filters to facilitate and simplify the search. As the study shows, each publisher has its own way of structuring catalogues and its own range of search criteria, but mostly it offers to choose by the following categories: type of product (books, souvenirs, merchandise, related products, etc.), type of book (printed or electronic), genre, subject matter, age group, design, top sales, promotions, new items, pre-sales.

The structure of catalogues is different for each publisher and has its own logic. “Nash Format” has the most extensive and detailed search system (a large number of criteria for selecting books, and each category has several subcategories and filters). Some publishers, such as “Folio” and “Old Lion Publishing House”, offer to use filters first, which will offer the site all the products you can choose from, while the products in the “sections” filter are not unified by one criterion. There are cases of not entirely reasonable division into categories, for example: on the website of the “Vivat” publishing house, e-books are classified into fiction and Ukrainian (it is clear that the latter category also includes fiction books).

4. The vast majority of publishers generally follow the rules for creating, structuring and filling their websites in the header, content and footer, except for minor deviations. The website categorisation and navigation is convenient and intuitive. The usability of the analysed websites fully meets the requirements set by experts.

Thus, despite the fact that the modern audience uses social media more often, websites remain a powerful tool in the PR activities of publishers due to their functional capabilities compared to social media. Recent studies show that publishers prefer online promotional activities, constantly change and improve their web resources using new PR technologies and website usability principles, which opens up prospects for further research.

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